

THE RELATIONSHIP OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND THE CLIMATE IN THE CLASSROOM BETWEEN TEACHERS AND STUDENTS, A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF BEING

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ABSTRACT

Within the classroom there are many situations with which teachers and students have to live to generate experiences, whether positive or negative. The present study investigates the influence of teacher emotional intelligence and the climate that develops in the classroom. According to the results, the students respond that the teacher must develop a more latent emotional intelligence, especially in exact science teachers, which generates a negative climate in the classroom in general. This is where the importance of establishing strategies for the teacher to reach the different dimensions such as personalization, participation, cohesion, satisfaction, task orientation, innovation and individualization and thus the teacher achieves self-awareness, empathy, self-confidence, motivation, self-control and social awareness.

Keywords: students, emotional intelligence, teachers, classroom climate.

INTRODUCTION

The development of Emotional Intelligence in the teacher is of great importance for an optimal climate in the classroom.

A review of approximately fifteen investigations related to the subject was carried out for the documentary study on the socio-emotional teaching competences between the year 2000 to the present day around the world, especially in Spanish and Spanish-speaking countries, although the most relevant references start from the year 2009 towards the present.

Most of the investigations have a quantitative approach based on the elaboration of instruments that allow to measure these socio-emotional competences, usually, they are based on instruments on emotional intelligence; being the survey the chosen method, in addition, the most studied subjects have been university teachers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical discussion on teaching socio-emotional competencies is carried out, the most relevant studies, being of a quantitative and qualitative nature.

Emotional Intelligence: approaches to the concept.

Mayer and Salovey (1990) defined the concept of “emotional intelligence” for the first time, although later in 1997 they reformulated their original idea, giving more importance to cognitive components and the ability to reflect on emotions. Since then, numerous publications have been made on this topic in the educational, organizational and health fields (Ciarrochi, Forgas and Mayer, 2006; Matthews, Zeidner and Roberts, 2007; Mestre and Fernández-Berrocal, 2007; Schulze and Roberts, 2005; Zeidner, Matthews and Roberts, 2009).

From the EI-ability model (Mayer and Salovey, 1997) a hierarchical structure of cognitive capacities is proposed for the adaptive management of emotions: perceive, facilitate, understand and manage or regulate emotions; This being the concept that Mayer and Salovey (1997) propose about socio-emotional competence.

Mayer & Salovey define emotional intelligence as “the ability to accurately perceive, value and express emotions; the ability to access and generate feelings that facilitate thinking; the ability to understand emotion and emotional awareness; and the ability to regulate emotions and promote emotional and intellectual growth ”(Mayer & Salovey, 1997: 10).

The development of Emotional Intelligence: Implications for teachers.

The basis for understanding teaching socio-emotional competencies, part of the knowledge, development and application of emotional intelligence.

It implies that teachers develop a greater capacity to identify, understand, regulate and think with emotions intelligently, they will have more resources to get students emotionally more prepared and to better cope with stressful events that frequently arise in the educational context. Our educational system is witnessing a very important process of transformation of study plans and a modification of compulsory schooling aimed at the integral development of the person focused on competencies (LOE, 2006).

Sometimes it is forgotten that these emotional, affective and social skills must be taught by a teaching team that masters these skills, since classrooms are for the student one of the most important socio-emotional learning models.

Emotional intelligence development.

Socialization, with its emotional aspects, finds a very adequate space in the school environment, as Extremera and Fernández Berrocal (2004) point out, not only because the student remains in the classroom for a large part of their childhood and adolescence, periods in which especially emotional development occurs, but because of the number of problems that arise in the educational field (school failure, violence, difficulties in coexistence, etc.), thereby demonstrating once again that the needs raised in educational institutions go beyond promoting the cognitive development of students, aiming to ensure that their students achieve comprehensive training, as one more consequence of the current conception of the role of affectivity and emotions in education, which shows that the cognitive configures the affective and the affective conditions the cognitive (Hernández, 2002).

Research by Fernández-Berrocal (2010) focused on analyzing the relationship between emotional intelligence and the teacher's personal adjustment point out that the teacher's emotional intelligence predicts the level of burnout they suffer (Brackett, Palomera & Mojsa, in press; Extremadura, Fernández – Berrocal & Durán, 2003). Furthermore, teachers experience more negative than positive emotions more frequently.

Class climate

The learning environments will allow constant interactions between student-teacher, student-student, student-experts, guests / community members, student-tools, student-content, student-environment.

The Aspen Institute (2021) considers the classroom observations can also be used to assess

the extent to which teachers are using instructional practices that foster positive social and emotional development, which is associated with classroom climate.

According to what constructivism is based on, it is about posing situations that promote the discovery and construction of knowledge by the student. In this case, the teacher has a place of mediation between knowledge and the student, mediation that is developed through a strategy that is oriented in this direction.

According to Azlin Norhaini, Mansor, Mohd & Zabil Ikhsan (2021) A school climate is defined as a pattern of shared perceptions of the characteristics and atmosphere, including its norms, values, and expectations of an organization with its members. In addition, a school climate is also defined as the quality and character of school life.

Method

The methodological approach will be developed through the correlational method, which is used when the purpose is to know the relationship between two or more concepts, categories or variables in a particular context. Associates variables through a predictable pattern for a group of settlers; offer predictions, explain the relationship between variables and quantify these relationships of the variables (Hernández Sampieri, 2014), this method stands out for the present research since it is desired to study the teacher's emotional intelligence as well as the teacher-student relationship and how this affects the development of the learning climate.

Hypothesis

- There are significant differences between the perception of the climate in the classroom of teachers and students.
- There are significant differences between the perception of the climate in the classroom according to the sex of the student.
- There are significant differences between the perception of the school climate of the students according to the grade they are in.
- There are significant differences in the emotional intelligence of men and women.
- There are significant differences in the emotional intelligence of teachers and students.
- There are significant differences in emotional intelligence according to the career they are studying.
- There is an association between the emotional intelligence of teachers and their students.
- There are significant correlations between the age of the students and their emotional intelligence.
- There is an association between emotional intelligence and sex.
- There is an association between the emotional intelligence of students and the career they are pursuing.

Sample

The type of sample is non-probabilistic, also called directed samples, they assume an informal selection procedure. From them, inferences are made about the population (Hernández Sampieri, 2014) in the Industrial Maintenance career in the subjects of Comprehensive Calculus, Electrical Machines, Industrial Service Networks, Digital Electronics, Programming Principles, Oral and Written Expression, Training Sociocultural I.

Instruments

For the measurement of the variables, the instruments will be validated; A suitable measurement instrument is one that records observable data that truly represents the concepts or variables that the researcher has in mind (Grinnell,

Williams & Unrau, 2009). In quantitative terms: the “reality” that you want to capture is truly captured. The instruments used are:

- Classroom Climate Inventory By Calvin College.
- Emotional Intelligence Teachers (Adapted From Emily Sterrett's Test.)

111 students, 91 men (82%), 20 women (18%) responded the test of emotional intelligence and climate in the classroom of the industrial maintenance career, the minimum age of the respondents is 17 years old, the maximum age is 23 years old with an average age of 18.8 meanwhile in the self-evaluation test of teacher emotional intelligence, 8 teachers of the same career responded.

Cronbach's alpha for the classroom climate test is 0.841, which is considered to be a high value of internal consistency in the test.

Through t-student, significant differences were sought between the perception of the school climate by men and women and only in 1 of the 50 items (2%) were significant differences found. This is the item (men have a better perception of this aspect from the climate in the classroom): 33. Class assignments are clear so that everyone knows what to do.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the test results, the students perceive that teachers consistently show Emotional Intelligence (EI), since their scores are above one standard deviation with respect to the mean.

Students perceive that teachers consistently do not show EI, since their scores are below one standard deviation with respect to the mean.

That is, students perceive that their teachers are not capable of expressing their points of view with honesty and thoughtfulness, without overwhelming (seen in the opposite sense, one could say they try to impose their points of view)

- Students perceive that their teachers frequently bring their negative emotions to the classroom and are unable to control their moods.
- The student perceives that their teachers do not pay their full attention to when they are listening.
- Students perceive that their teachers do not consider that teaching work makes sense and adds value to society.

Atudents perceive that their teachers cannot persuade others to adopt their views without coercion.

According to the test of Classroom Climate: the students perceive an organized class and do not consider their classes to be a waste of time but for example in this ítems they perceive there's a negative classroom climate:

- Students constantly observe the clock during class
- The seats or tables in this class are arranged in the same way in each session.
- Students seem to do the same kinds of activities in all classes.
- It takes a long time to get to know everyone by first name in this class.

- Students can choose the activities and how they will work.
- The teacher often thinks of unusual class activities.
- New and different ways of teaching are seldom used in this class.
- Students don't have many opportunities to meet in this class.
- The class is made up of people who don't know each other well.
- The teams in the class are organized with the same students in each sesión.

CONCLUSION

Something that draws attention is how students point out that teachers express negative emotions in class giving way to a tense or stressful classroom climate, in addition to generating situations where students are not classmates, they are individuals who separately they perform tasks, that is, there is no companionship. Even so, the teacher teaches an organized class but the majority of the lack of emotional intelligence is pointed out.

It is in the exact science classes where there are more deficiencies in emotional intelligence than in the sciences based on human values and interpersonal relationships.

It is here where the need to undertake improvement strategies in the teacher is shown because with a negative climate in the classroom, learning is not the same.

It is expected to reach a conflict resolution and support the teacher in his self-knowledge so that he can develop an enriching class, with a climate in the classroom where not only the student learns but also the teacher.

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